

Title: New type Reprogramming by hyaluronan tetra-saccharides, which is endogenously produced, through sirtuins, growth factors and high molecular weight hyaluronan

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Abstract

Background

Regenerative medicine of “iPS cells” and “Direct reprogramming” require tissue engineering and transplantation in patients. Their much time and high cost should put pressure on healthcare economics. HA4 requires neither tissue engineering nor transplantation.

Following effects of HA4 were reported:

- (1) Hyaluronan tetra-saccharides (HA4) induced expression of heat shock protein 72 and of brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and production of high MW hyaluronan (HWHHA). These molecules are known to facilitate Reprogramming
- (2) HA4 showed recovery of walking ability in a rat spinal cord injury.
- (3) HA4 was endogenously detected in the tissues of the spinal cord injury.

These reports indicate that HA4 has effects of Reprogramming followed by tissue Regeneration.

Methods

Sperms digest HA around oocytes for fertilization through hyaluronidase, PH20, which degrade HA into HA4. HA4 was added in the fertilization invitro and the growth rate was measured. The fertilized oocyte is a totipotent stem cell, a top of stem cells hierarchy, suggesting that HA4 shows effects on the other stem cells. HA4 was added in epidermal and neural stem cells, the 3rd of the hierarchy and cells were immunoi-stained, and sirtuins, which is known to bring about tissue Regeneration, CD44 toll like receptor 2 and 4, and HMWHA were analyzed. Moreover human fibroblasts at Hayflick limit were treated with HA to observe by electron-microscopy.

RESULTS

In many kinds of cells, proliferation is not compatible with differentiation. However, HA4 differentiated human neural stem cells into neurons (β III Tubulin) while maintaining stem cell characteristics (nestin). We previously reported that HA4 induced recovery of walking ability supported by histological and electro-physiological examinations in a rat spinal cord injury, indicating that the functions of β III Tubulin⁺ and nestin⁺ neurons are normal.

Moreover, HA4 simultaneously induced de-differentiation, proliferation and differentiation in organotypic 3D rat epidermal keratinocytes (REKs). HA4 induced stem cell molecular marker (Δ NP63), proliferation marker (Ki67) and basal cell marker (Keratin 14) in spinous-granular layer which normally contain only differentiated cells. These expressions are ectopic ones indicating de-differentiation. Expression of the differentiation molecular marker, filaggrin in the spinous-granular layers were enhanced by HA4. HA4 improved atopic dermatitis, indicating that

the skin containing the spinous-granular layers which consist of stem (Δ NP63⁺, Ki67⁺, Keratin 14⁺) and differentiated (filaggrin⁺) cells is not abnormal.

DNA microarray-ontology in human keratinocytes showed that HA4 up-regulated HGF and FGF1, and induced both proliferation and differentiation

Furthermore, in REKs, HA4 induced expressions of SIRT1 and HMWHA which are known to facilitate tissue Regeneration. It was reported that either SIRT1 or HGF induced both proliferation and differentiation.

In human senescent fibroblasts at Hayflick limit, electron-microscopy showed that HA4 induced a lot of very long mitochondria and Autophagy which are known to be in charge of Reprogramming and of suppressing cellular senescence. In addition to it, HA4 inhibited expressions of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL6, TNF α , IL1 β) in U937 cells. Therefore, HA4 can suppress inflammation and senescence which often occur in environment surrounding tissues that are subject to Regenerative Medicine in patients.

These various effects of HA4 should be due to multi-functions of SIRT1 which are known to be up-regulated by HGF and FGF1. Therefore, topical administration with HA4 facilitated rabbit corneal wound healing. The efficacy of HA4 is stronger than that of exogenous HMWHA, a topical medicine for dry eyes, which cannot permeate inter-cellular space because of its big molecular size.

CONCLUSIONS

Effects of HA4 are multi-dimensional, because HA4 induces many molecules with multi-faces, i.e., SIRT1, HGF, FGF1, Hsp72 and HMWHA, and promotes incompatible things, i.e., proliferation vs differentiation, stem vs differentiated cells. However, these things strongly indicate that HA4 has a potential for Regenerative Medicine through the new type partial Reprogramming.

Keywords hyaluronan tetra-saccharides (HA4), regenerative medicine, tissue regeneration, SIRT1, newt, Reprogramming, de-differentiation, stem cells, differentiated cells, autophagy

INTRODUCTION

iPS cells are produced through “de-differentiation” (1) “Direct reprogramming”, a cutting-edge method of regenerative medicine has emerged (2). This can induce objective cells from differentiated cells directly in vitro.

HA4 is produced through degrading HA by testicular hyaluronidases and blood Hyal-1 (3, 4). We previously showed that HA4 suppressed hyperthermia-induced cell death through up-regulating heat shock protein 72 (Hsp70 family) in vitro, and in vivo neural cell death and Astrogliosis in murine brain ischemia (5-7). The Hsp70 is in charge of tissue Regeneration (8). We demonstrated that HA4 improved walking ability on a grid and beam indicated by histological and electro-physiological examinations in a rat spinal cord injury (9). Wakao et al. showed that HA4 induced axonal regeneration in the rat spinal cord injury (10). Wang et al. reported that HA4 was endogenously produced in the cerebrospinal fluid for self-repair in the rat spinal cord injury (11, 12). Hyal-1 is known to be activated by acidic environment, indicating that Hyal-1 was activated by the injury-induced inflammatory acidic environment (4). It was also reported that HA4 promotes regeneration of peripheral nerve (13). These effects described above indicate that HA4 generates in situ tissue regeneration.

Stem cells are usually categorized as “multipotent” (able to give rise to multiple cells within a lineage), “pluripotent” (able to give rise to all cell types in an adult) and “totipotent” (able to give rise to all embryonic and adult lineages) (14, 15). Fertilized eggs are totipotent stem cells, i.e., tops of stem cell hierarchy (14, 15). Epidermal stem cells and neural stem cells are useful to investigate differentiation and proliferation and self-renewal, because molecular markers of stem cells and many differentiated cells were established (16, 17). These cells were used in the present study to investigate effects of HA4 on the stem cells categorized in multipotent stem cells in the 3rd of the stem cell hierarchy (16, 17).

Kage at al. reported that HA4 induced hyaluronan synthase 3 (HAS3) in skin fibroblasts (18). High molecular weight HA (HMWHA) facilitates tissue regeneration (19, 20). This coincides with our report showing that expression of HA increased just after injury and decreased immediately after close of the injury in rabbit corneal wound healing (21). CD44 expression was synchronous with the HA change (21). Therefore, rabbit corneal wound healing model was used in the present study too.

It was shown that SIRT1 promotes tissue regeneration containing reprogramming, both proliferation and differentiation like HA4 (22-24). Therefore, effects of HA4 on expressions of sirtuin family (proteins, mRNAs, deacetylase activities) were investigated.

Finally we performed DNA microarray in human keratinocytes to comprehensively investigate effects of HA4.

Materials and Methods

Test substances

We produced and analyzed HA4 used in the present study according to the methods of our previous report [25]. Molecular weight and purity of the HA4 were determined by anion-exchange HPLC (Shimazu, Kyoto), Fluorophore-assisted carbohydrate electrophoresis (FACE) [25].

HA4 (catalog no. HA4^{AN}), HA5 (catalog no. HA5^{AA}), HA6 (catalog no. HA6^{AN}), HA8 (catalog no. HA8^{AN}) and HA10 (catalog no. HA10^{AN}) were purchased from Contipro (endotoxin ≤ 0.05 IU/mg, Dolni Dobrouc, Czech Republic) to use these materials as standards or to compare effects with HA4. Contipro shows that molecular weights were determined by mass. The MW of the HA4 (catalog no. HA4^{AN}) is 776.2. The MW of HA4 that we previously produced using testicular hyaluronidase was 775.1 [25].

Δ HA2 (unsaturated HA2, catalog no. HA02), Δ HA4 (unsaturated HA4, catalog no. HA04), Δ di-C0S (Δ UA-GalNAc, catalog no. CD001) and Δ CS4 (unsaturated chondroitin sulfate AD 4 mers, catalog no. CS004) were purchased from Iduron (Manchester UK). The oligosaccharides are separated by high resolution gel filtration and purity was assessed on an analytical Superdex S75 HPLC column (Data Sheets for profiles of Iduron). These were applied in an ultrafiltration discs, 1 kDa NMW (PLAC02510 Regenerated Cellulose Membrane Filter, 1 kDa NMWCO) before using as working solutions in cell culture to remove endotoxins.

Endotoxin free 35 kDa HA (catalog no. HA20K-1) and 900 kDa HA (catalog no. HA1M-1) were obtained from Lifecore (GMP, pre-clinical to clinical, ≤ 0.05 EU/mg, MN, USA).

The HA4 used in the present experiments was treated with chondroitinase ABC (Chase ABC; C3667, Sigma). Normally, the digestion products are Δ HA2 and normal HA2 (HA2). The HA2 was used as a negative control. HA 3 mers (HA3; GlcNAc-GlcA-GlcNAc) was generously gifted from Leiden Institute of Chemistry (Leiden, Holland). Resveratrol was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (MW: 228. 24, 554325, MO, USA). These substances were applied in an ultrafiltration discs, 1 kDa NMW (PLAC02510 Regenerated Cellulose Membrane Filter, 1 kDa NMWCO) before using as working solutions in cell culture to remove endotoxins.

Endotoxin

In vitro, monocytes and macrophages were activated to synthesize IL-1 β and TNF- α by concentration of LPS at 0.05 EU/mL [26]. Endotoxin was determined with Pyro GeneTM rFC (0.005-5 EU/mL; Lonza). Endotoxin levels of every working solutions used in the present experiments are below detection limit (0.005 EU/mL). For example, the endotoxin level in 1 mg/ml of HA4 was estimated as 0.00419EU/ml.

Analysis of HA4

The HA4 used in the present experiments were treated with eliminase chondroitinase ABC. When chondroitinase ABC does not digest the HA4, the HA4 structure is impaired.

One mg of HA4 was digested with 0.01 units of chondroitinase ABC in 0.1 M sodium acetate buffer, pH 6.0 at 37 °C for 20 hrs. The reaction was stopped by heating at 100 °C for 3 min. HA4 was treated with pre-heated chondroitinase ABC in the same way as a negative control. Chondroitinase ABC digestion of normal HA4 produces 2 disaccharides, one with an unsaturated uronate (Δ HA2) and one normal HA2 (HA2) [27].

The digestion products and the HA4 were analyzed by anion exchange HPLC and FACE according to our previous report and so on [25, 27].

Anion exchange HPLC

Normal phase HPLC was done using YMC-pack NH₂ (4.0 × 250 mm, YMC, Kyoto, Japan). The HA oligosaccharides were eluted with a linear gradient of 2–100% 0.8 M NaH₂PO₄ at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min at 40 °C. Absorbance was monitored at 210 nm. HA 4 mers (Contipro), HA 6 mers (Contipro) and HA 8 mers (Contipro) were used as standards. Contipro shows that molecular weights of these HA oligosaccharides were determined by mass spectrometry.

FACE

FACE was performed according to the following protocol of Midura et al [28]. Δdi-HA (Iduron), Δdi-C0S (Iduron), HA4 (Contipro), HA6 (Contipro) and HA8 (Contipro) were used as standards.

- (1) AMAC (2-Aminoacridone, 06627, Sigma -Aldrich) labeling
AMAC solution: 0.54 mg AMAC 77 mg NaBH₃CN in 0.4 mL of DMSO, 0.1ml of glacial acetic acid and 0.5 ml of water. The oligosaccharides (5 nmol) was incubated with 40 μl of the AMAC solution for 16 hrs at 37 °C in dark.
- (2) Electrophoresis
 - 1) Acrylamide Gel Solution: 500 ml of 40% acrylamide (37.5:1), 100 ml of Tris-Acetate solution (400 mM, pH 7.0), 375 ml pure water and 25 ml glycerol
 - 2) Conditions of electrophoresis
Constant voltage: 500 V, beginning of electrophoresis: 30 mA/gel, End of run: 15 mA/gel, Running time: 50 ~ 60 min, Keep low temperature (4 °C)
 - 3) Images were acquired with GelDoc Go (BIO-RAD)

Murine fertilized eggs

Murine fertilized eggs were cultured in standard in vitro fertilization medium just after adding sperms in the presence and absence of HA4 (1, 10, 10 and 1000 ng/ml) or of 900 kDa HA (1000 ng/ml) for 48 hrs according to the method of Kawamura [29]. The ratios of (number of morula stage eggs/number of 2 cell stage eggs) x 100 were measured.

REKs culture

Organotypic REKs were cultured in trans-wells according to the method of MacCallum [30]. To prepare basement membranes MDCK2 cells (CRL-2936™ ATCC) were seeded onto the Falcon® Permeable Support (trans-well) for 12 well plates with 0.4 μm Transparent PET Membrane (353180) at a high density (100,000 cells/trans-well) in DMEM with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) with high glucose (4,500 mg/L). The cells were allowed to grow for 7 days, by which time they have established a basement membrane on the trans-well surface. The cells were removed by detergent (0.5% NP40) lysis and the trans-well surface washed. Then, REKs were seeded onto the basement membrane on the trans-wells at a density of 100,000 cells per trans-well. The seeded REKs were then immersed in DMEM/10% FBS with low glucose (1000 mg/L) present both in the upper and lower chambers of the trans-wells. At 4 days after seeding (Day 0) REKs reach confluence. From Day 0 the apical surfaces of the REKs were exposed to air by removing the culture media from the upper chamber and leaving culture media in the bottom wells. The media in the lower chambers were changed every other day for the duration of the experiment. REKs were treated with and without the test compounds described above solved in the same culture media for 9 days.

Human adult epidermal keratinocytes (DS Pharma Biomedical, Japan) were cultured (30,000/well of 96 well plate) for 24 hrs, then treated for 24 h with the test compounds described above in DMEM with 10 % FBS with no added growth factors.

Δ HA2, HA4, Δ HA4, HA6 and HA8, 35 kDa HA, 900 kDa HA or Δ CS4 at 10 ng/ml, and with resveratrol (Sigma) at 10 ng/ml. HA4 was used at 0.01, 0.1, 1 or 100 ng/ml in REKs or in human keratinocytes too. Resveratrol was also used at 10 ng/ml or 685 ng/ml (3 μ M) in human keratinocyte cultures, since it was reported that resveratrol induces SIRT1 protein at 3 μ M [31]. Resveratrol was dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at 70 mM (16 mg/ml) and delivered to cells in media containing this solvent at the final concentration of culture media.

Histology

The REKs tissues were processed as follows:

- 1) Embedded in paraffin after fixation with 2 % paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (PB).
- 2) Cut into sections.
- 3) After deparaffinizing in xylene, alcohol (100, 90, 70, 50 %) and running water followed by retrieving antigen by treatment with Retrieve-All Antigen Unmasking System 1 (Covance, USA).
- 4) Dissolved 1st or 2nd antibody in 0.1 M PB containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA). The sections were incubated in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA for 1 hr at room temperature to avoid non-specific binding of the antibodies.
- 5) Without washing, the sections were incubated with 1st and 2nd antibodies in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA overnight at 4 °C and for 1 hr at room temperature, respectively.
- 6) The sections were washed with 0.01 M PBS 3 times between the steps except for 4) and 5).

The antibodies described below were obtained from Abcam (Cambridge, UK). 1st antibody : against Δ Np63 (ab203826), Ki67 (ab15580), K10 (ab76318), K14 (ab7800), filaggrin (ab221155), TLR2 (ab209216), TLR4 (ab9100), SIRT1 (ab110304), SIRT2 (ab134171), SIRT3 (ab217319), SIRT4 (ab231137), SIRT5 (ab259967), SIRT6 (ab191385), SIRT7 (ab259968) or CD44 (ab254530)

Sections were also treated with biotinylated HA binding protein (385911, Sigma-Aldrich) or stained with Hematoxylin-Eosin (H.E.).

Non-immune immunoglobulins of which classes are same as the first antibodies (ab313801, ab281590) were used as negative controls in the immuno-staining (data not shown).

Fluorescence conjugated secondary antibodies or streptavidin (ab15077, ab150080, ab150113, ab150115, ab277701) were used to visualize the stainings. Mounting medium with DAPI (ab104139) was used for nuclear staining. Sections were pre-treated with hyaluronidase from Streptomyces hyalurolyticus (389561-100U, Sigma-Aldrich) as a negative control of HA staining.

These sections stained with fluorescent reagents were observed with Leica confocal laser scan microscope. H.E. staining was observed with a Leica upright light microscope.

Keratinocytes monolayers were immuno-stained by anti-SIRT1 (ab110304) in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA after fixation with 2 % paraformaldehyde followed by 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA. The tissues were incubated with 3% hydrogen peroxide to block endogenous peroxidase then with HRP conjugated anti-rabbit IgG (ab205718) followed by 0.05% 3,3'-

diaminobenzidine (DAB)- 0.015% hydrogen peroxide in 0.01M phosphate buffered saline (PBS), pH 7.2. The tissue sections were observed with Olympus upright light microscope.

Number of positive cells per area ($215 \times 165 \mu\text{m}^2$) of fibroblasts monolayer stained for SA-beta-Gal were blindly counted with a Keyence All-in-One Fluorescence Microscope, BZ-X700 by a third person.

Human neuro-spheres

Human neuro-spheres (Lonza) were treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4 25 ng/ml, of brain neurotrophic growth factor (BDNF) or of combination of HA4 and BDNF in DMEM/10% FBS with low glucose (1000 mg/L) for 12 days. These samples were observed with the Keyence inverted microscope.

The neuro-spheres treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4 were immuno-stained for nestin (a specific marker of neural stem cells; antibody: mouse monoclonal, ab22035, Abcam) and β III tubulin (a specific marker of neurons; antibody: rabbit IgG, ab229590, Abcam) followed by Alexa Fluor® 647-Goat Anti-Mouse IgG H&L (ab150115 Abcam) and Alexa Fluor® 488-Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG H&L (ab150077, Abcam) after fixed in 2 % paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M PB followed by 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA. The samples were washed in 0.01 M PBS 3 times between steps. The neuro-spheres were observed with the Keyence fluorescent microscope.

Rabbit corneal wound healing model

Rabbit corneal wound healing model was made according to the method of Asari et. al., [21]. This experiment was performed under the experiment ethics of Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries in Japan. Corneas were topically treated with 1 ml of physiological saline, of HA4 (1 mg/ml) or of 900 kDa HA (1 mg/ml; Hyalein; Santen, Tokyo) after treatment of an n-heptanol (100 μ l) immersed circle filter paper with 1 cm diameter for 1 min. Wound was stained with fluorescent dye and photographed without changing shooting condition containing a focus by Nikon single-Lens Reflex Camera. Then, the fluorescent areas were measured by Image J.

Cell culture to assess sirtuins

REKs treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4 were immuno-stained for sirtuin family SIRT1-7. REKs treated with and without 10 ng/ml of Δ HA2, HA4, Δ HA4, HA6 were used for SIRT1 western blotting. REKs incubated with and without 0.01, 0.1 and 1.0 ng/ml of HA4 were treated for SIRT1 qRT-PCR.

Human keratinocytes treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4 for 24 hrs were immuno-stained for SIRT1. Moreover, human keratinocytes were treated with and without 10 pg/ml, 100 pg/ml, 1 ng/ml or 10 ng/ml of HA4 for 24 hrs to access low concentrations of HA4 to promote SIRT1. Furthermore, human keratinocytes were treated with and without 685 ng/ml of resveratrol, or 10 ng/ml of HA2, HA4, HA5, HA6, 10 kDa HA, 50 kDa HA or 900 kDa HA to access SIRT1 stainability by several molecular weight of HA. Then, these keratinocytes were immuno-stained for SIRT1 as described in **Histology**.

To access SIRT1 mRNA expression (qRT-PCR), the human keratinocytes were treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4, HA6, HA10, 35 kDa HA, 900 kDa HA and resveratrol. The human keratinocytes were treated with and without 10 ng/ml of Δ HA2, HA3, HA4, HA6, 35 kDa HA, 900 kDa HA or of Δ CS4 or of 685 ng/ml (3 μ M) resveratrol for SIRT1 deacetylase activity assay. For SIRT3 or SIRT6 immuno-staining, REKs were

treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4. For SIRT6 deacetylase activity assay, the human keratinocytes were treated with and without 10 ng/ml of Δ HA2, HA4, HA6, 35 kDa HA, 900 kDa HA or resveratrol.

Western Blotting for SIRT1

REKs were analyzed by standard western blotting method by using Criterion TGX™ Precast Gels and electrophoresis systems from BIO-RAD. After SDS-PAGE followed by transfer to a Poly Vinylidene Fluoride membrane, the membrane was immuno-stained with rabbit anti-SIRT1 (ab110304, Abcam) and with polyclonal rabbit anti-GAPDH antibody (sc-25778, Santa Cruz) followed by HRP conjugated anti-rabbit IgG. Then DAB was applied to the membrane.

Quantitative RT-PCR of SIRT1

SIRT1 mRNA expression was determined by qRT-PCR. RNA was isolated from the human keratinocytes using PureLink™ RNA Mini Kit Invitrogen™. NanoDrop-1000 (ThermoFisher) was used to identify RNA concentration and purity determined by the 260 A/280 A ratio. cDNA was obtained using High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (ThermoFisher). RT-PCR was performed on QuantStudio 7 (ThermoFisher) using Fast SYBR™ Green Master Mix (ThermoFisher) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Relative changes in gene expression were normalized to GAPDH with the $\Delta\Delta$ Cq method. Primer (Hs_SIRT1_1_SG QuantiTect Primer Assay, GeneGlobe ID- QT00051261, Catalog No. - 249900) for SIRT1 was purchased from Qiagen.

SIRT1 or SIRT6 deacetylase activity

Whole cell extracts including nucleus were prepared using Nuclear and Cytoplasmic Extraction reagent, NE-PER by Thermo Scientific Pierce (Rockford, IL, USA). The SIRT1 or SIRT6 deacetylase activity was measured with CycLex® SIRT1/Sir2 Deacetylase Fluorometric Assay Kit or with CycLex® SIRT6 Deacetylase Fluorometric Assay Kit. The values were adjusted with protein concentrations. Recombinant SIRT1 with NAD (+) and recombinant SIRT1 with NAD (-) contained in the kit were used as a positive and negative control of the measurement, respectively. The same controls in the kit for SIRT6 were used as well.

Passages-induced cellular senescence

Primary murine dermal fibroblasts were isolated from the skin of C57BL/6J mouse pups at 2–3 days of age according to the method of Wang et al. [32]. The fibroblasts were seeded at 30,000/well of 10 cm well plate. We found that 4 passages the fibroblasts induced cellular senescence. Cellular senescence was detected by senescence-associated beta-galactosidase staining (SA-beta Gal staining) with the kit of Biovision (CA, USA). The cells in 2 passages were used as young cells control. The cells were incubated for 24 hrs with Δ HA2 and normal HA2, HA4, HA6 or 900 kDa HA at 10 ng/ml, and resveratrol at 3 μ M (685 ng/ml) in 4 passages. Numbers of SA-beta Gal staining positive cells per 0.135 mm² were blindly counted by a third person.

Hayflick limit

Human fibroblasts (number of seeding cells: 100/ dish) in dishes (150 mm) were cultured in DMEM containing 10% FBS and 1 g/L for 40 days. Then, these cells were treated with and

without HA4 (10 ng/ml), HA4 (10 ng/ml) + EXT527 (20 nM), resveratrol (1000 ng/ml) and 900 kDa HA (1000 ng/ml) for 10 days. Passage was not done to avoid damage induced by the passage.]

Dishes from each group were treated with Mito Tracker® red CMXRos for assay of mitochondrial membrane potentials. Moreover, antibody to LC2 (Invitrogen LC3A/LC3B Polyclonal Antibody) followed by Alexa Fluor® 647-Goat Anti-Mouse IgG H&L (ab150115 Abcam) were used for immuno-staining.

The other dishes from each group were immuno-stained for SIRT1 as described in **Histology**.

Further other dishes were processed for transmission electron microscopy. The cells were processed as follows:

- 1) Fixed with 2% paraformaldehyde and 2% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 for 1 hr and post-fixed with 1% OsO₄ for 10 min.
- 2) Dehydrated with graded ethanol (50-100%) for 10 min each.
- 3) Put in xylene (twice) for 10 min each.
- 4) Put in xylene + epoxy resin (1:1), xylene + epoxy resin (1:2) and epoxy resin (100%; twice) for 1 day each. Epoxy resin: epon812 (48%), DDSA (30%), NMA (20%), DMP-30 (2%).
- 5) Embedded in the epoxy resin, then to harden the epoxy resin, the samples were placed in an oven at 60° C for 48 hrs.
- 6) The epoxy resin blocks of 5) were cut into ultrathin sections with an ultramicrotome (Reichert, Ultracut N). The sections were mounted on copper grids.
- 7) After staining with uranyl acetate and lead citrate, the sections were observed with a Philips transmission electron microscope.

ELISA to detect cytokines

IL-1 β , IL-6 or TNF- α sandwich ELISA kit (96 well plate; Invitrogen; # BMS224-2HS, # EH2IL6, # KAC1751) was used.

- 1) add 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA and incubated for 1 hr at room temperature.
- 2) add 100 μ l of culture media and incubated at 4 °C overnight.
- 3) add biotinylated antibodies against IL1 β , IL6 or TNF α in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA overnight at 4 °C.
- 4) add streptavidin conjugated horse radish peroxidase in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA and incubated for 1 hr at room temperature.
- 5) add chromogen contained in the kit and incubated for 10 min at room temperature.
- 6) add stop solution contained in the kit.
- 7) washed with 0.1 M PB 3 times between the steps.
- 8) measured intensity of the solutions with a plate reader (Molecular Device SpectraMax®).

Binding assay of HA4 and TLR4

- 1) Incubate 1 nmol of HA4 with 1 nmol of recombinant human TLR4 (R & D system, 1478-TR-050), 1 nmol of HA4 with 1 nmol of heated TLR4, and 1 nmol of HA4 only overnight at 4 °C. These were dissolved in 0.1 M PB containing 1% BSA.
- 2) Apply them in Amicon Ultra Centrifugal Filter, 30 kDa MWCO.
- 3) Centrifuge 14,000 rpm for 30 min.
- 4) Obtain bottom solution. When HA4 binds TLR4, HA4 cannot move to the bottom through the filter in the centrifugation.

5) FACE to detect HA4.

Exogenous TLR4 on an effect of HA4

Ca9-22 cells (National Institutes of Biomedical Innovation, Health and Nutrition), a kind of epithelial cells in a 96 wells plate were incubated in culture media with and without a culture media containing 600 μ M (1.08 μ g/ml) of hydrogen peroxide for 1 hr. After washing, these cells were incubated with and without 100 ng/ml of HA4 or 100 ng/ml of HA4 plus 10 μ g/ml of recombinant TLR4/MD2 (R&D Systems, 3146-TM-050/CF; <1.0 EU per 1 μ g of the protein by the LAL method.) for 3 hrs. Then, these cells were applied in MTS assay to assess cell proliferation and cell viability.

DNA microarray

The RNAs of human keratinocytes treated with and without 10 ng/ml of HA4 were subjected to microarray full service and assessed using a CodeLink Human Whole Genome Bioarray (GE Healthcare/Amersham Biosciences). The array is comprised of approximately 55,000 30-mer probes designed to conserved exons across the transcripts of targeted genes. Biotinylated cRNA samples from aliquots of total RNA were hybridized to the array, incubated with streptavidin-Cy5 and scanned. After intensity data were normalized, a significant up-regulation was defined as a fold change ≥ 2.0 , and a significant down-regulation was defined as fold change ≤ 0.50 . Data regarding proliferation, differentiation, cell death and senescence were extracted, and analyzed with Pathway of GO, Ontology by Microarray Data Analysis Tool (Filgen).

Statistical analysis

Paired t-test, Dunnet or Tukey multiple comparison test was used for comparing means. The results were considered significant with P-values smaller than 0.05.

RESULTS

Analysis of HA4

Fig. 1A shows the anion exchange HPLC analyses to determine the purity and molecular size of the HA4 used in the present study. Panels a, b and c of Fig. 1A show the standards of HA4 (sHA4), HA6 (sHA6) and HA8 (sHA8) from Contipro, respectively (Fig. 1A). The peak of the HA4 used in the present study (panel d, Fig. 1A) is same as one of the sHA4 (panel a, Fig. 1A). The Fluorophore-assisted carbohydrate electrophoresis (FACE) provides another analysis of the HA4, which shows a single band at the site of sHA4 (lane 3 of panel f, Fig. 1A).

When HA4 loses HA structure, chondroitinase ABC cannot digest the HA4 (27). The chondroitinase ABC eliminase digest of HA4 yielded a very clear Δ HA2 & HA2 band (arrow, lane 2 of panel f, Fig. 1A) or peak that contains the intact HA2 derived from the HA4 non-reducing end and the Δ HA2 released from the reducing end by the eliminase (* panel e, Fig. 1A). The heat inactivated chondroitinase ABC (hChase) did not yield the two disaccharides (Δ HA2 & HA2, lane 4 of f, Fig. 1A). Therefore, molecular structure of HA4 is one of HA (Fig. 1B). The MW of the HA4 (catalog no. HA4^{AN}) from Contipro is 776.2. The MW of our HA4 is 775.1 (25).

The results in Fig. 1 guarantee the molecular sizes and purity of the HA4 used in the following experiments.

HA4-induced proliferation, differentiation and de- differentiation

Tissue Regeneration of newts, i.e., epimorphosis was performed through the partial Reprogramming in which cells contain characteristics of both stem and differentiated cells (33, 34). Thus, characteristics of stem and differentiated cells were analyzed in keratinocytes containing epidermal stem cells and neural stem cells.

HA4 promoted cell division in murine fertilized oocytes from 2 cells to morula stage (Fig. 2A1). The treatment with 900 kDa HA did not elicit any change (Fig. 2A1). Fig. 2A2 shows that HA4 is produced immediately before fertilization and bind TLR4 to induce signal transduction.

The basal layer is the only layer with proliferative potential in epidermis. Proliferating cells indicated by Ki67 are found even in the upper-most layer just under corneum of 3 dimensional organotypic rat epidermal keratinocytes (REKs) treated with HA4 at Day 5 (Arrow heads, Fig. 2B1). HA4 increased the number of Ki67⁺ cells at Day 0 and Day 5 (Fig. 2B-2). HA4 proliferated NIH-3T3 cells too (Fig. 2C).

HA4 enhanced expression of filaggrin at granular layers (Fig. 2D).

HA4 (10 ng/ml) and HA4 (10 ng/ml) + BDNF (25 ng/ml) but not BDNF (25 ng/ml) alone induced dendritic outgrowth of the human neuro-spheres (Fig. 2E1 a-d). HA4 (10 ng/ml) induced β III tubulin expression (a marker of neurons) while maintaining nestin (a marker of neural stem cells) (Fig. 2E2 c and d). BDNF (100 ng/ml) induced β III tubulin expression and decreased nestin expression (Fig. 2E2 e and f).

Effects of HA4 on SIRT1 expression and cellular senescence at Hayflick limit.

The results described above show that HA4 has multi-functions of proliferation, differentiation as shown in SIRT1 (22-24). Therefore, we investigated effects of HA4 on SIRT1 multi-dimensionally and on cellular senescence that SIRT1 suppresses (35). SIRT1 was immunopositive in REKs and human keratinocytes (Fig. 3A and 3B). SIRT1 was induced even at 0.01 ng/ml (Fig. 3C). Resveratrol (R) and HA5 slightly induced SIRT1 of which intensity is weaker than that of HA4 (Fig. 3D).

Western blotting and qRT-PCR showed HA4 up-regulated protein expression in REKs and mRNA expression in human keratinocytes, respectively (Fig. 3E and 3F). HA4 also promoted SIRT1 and SIRT6 deacetylase activity in human keratinocytes (Fig. 3G, 3H and 3I). The SIRT1 deacetylase activity was induced in a concentration dependent manner (Fig. 3G). Resveratro and HA3 slightly induced SIRT1 activity (Fig. 3H). HA4 did not show obvious change in SIRT2, SIRT3, SIRT4, SIRT5 and SIRT7 in the sirtuin family consist of 7 molecules (data not shown).

Suppression of cellular senescence and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines by HA4

Environmental tissues around the tissue which need Regenerative medicine contain cellular senescence and/or inflammation, indicating that the tissues brought by Regenerative Medicine should be damaged (36, 37). Therefore, the patients must simultaneously receive anti-ageing and the tissue Regeneration treatments. SIRT1 has the both effects (22-24).

We found that 4 passages induces cellular senescence. HA4 suppressed cellular senescence of murine skin fibroblasts induced by 4 passage (Fig. 4A).

Moreover, we investigated the effects of HA4 on the heaviest cellular senescence, i.e., one at Hayflick limit in the present study. Cellular senescence rapidly progressed between Day 40 and Day 50 in cultured human fibroblasts (Fig. 4b and 4c). The fibroblasts show enlargement, i.e., hypertrophy and inclusion bodies at Day 50 (Fig. 4c). Fibroblasts treated with HA4 between Day 40 and 50 do not show such changes (Fig. 4c and 4d). Electron-microscopy indicates that the fibroblasts at Day 50 include large phago-lysosomes which should correspond the inclusion bodies shown by light microscopy (Orange arrows, Fig. 4c, 4e and 4f). The large phago-lysosomes should be formed because of a little digestion, which is induced by deficiency of SIRT1 (38). At Day 50 HA4-treated fibroblasts contain many small phgao-lysosomes which are autophagic vacuoles according to their morphology by electron-microscopy (39).

Both fibroblasts of No-addition control at Day 40 and ones treated with HA4 at Day 50 contain many autophagic vacuoles and mitochondria (Fig. 4Bg-i). Fig. 4C1 and 4C2 showed that LC3a and LC3b (markers of autophagic vacuoles) expressions and mitochondrial membrane potential were maintained by HA4 but not 900 kDa HA and resveratrol treatment and were down-regulated by EXT527, an inhibitor of SIRT1 at Day 50.

HA4 suppressed pro-inflammatory cytokines, IL6, TNF α and IL1 β in U937 cells treated with PMA and LPS (Fig. 4D). The present effects are due to SIRT1 which inactivates NF- κ B through de-acetylating to suppress pro-inflammatory cytokine expression (40).

Promoted HA production, CD44 expression and corneal wound healing by HA4, and effects of HA4 on Toll like receptor (TLR) 2 and 4 in REKs, and TLR4 binding assay with HA4

HA4 promoted production of HA in REKs (Fig. 5A1). The HA is localized in inter-cellular matrix and corneum (Fig. 5A2). Arrows in Fig. 5A2 indicate inter-cellular bridges. Hyaluronidase from *Streptomyces hyalurolyticus* which is specific for HA abolished the HA staining with biotinylated HA binding protein from chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans in bovine cartilage, indicating that these HA staining is specific for HA (Fig. 5A3) (41). HA4 induced HAS2 (Fig. 5A4) but not HAS1 and HAS3 (data not shown). The HAS2 staining was detected near cell membrane indicating mature HAS2, and in cytoplasm indicating synthesizing HAS2 (Fig. 5A4).

HA4 up-regulated CD44 expressions (Fig. 5B).

The area of wound of HA4-but not 900 kDa HA-treated corneas is statistically significantly different from one of P. Saline control (P.S., Fig. 5C1b and 5C2b). Epithelial tissues of P. S are

monolayers (Fig. 5C3). On the other hand, epithelial tissues of P. S. or of 900 kDa HA consist of a few layers (Fig. 5C3). However, the epithelial cells of 900 Da HA are thinner than those of HA4, indicating that HA4-treated epithelial cells are matured more than those of 900 kDa HA (Fig. 5C3).

TLR2 and TLR4 immuno-staining in REKs were not changed by HA4 (Fig. 5D1). Corneum staining is artifact that are common in dermatopathology due to several factors (42). Immuno-stainabilities in corneum (co) in Fig. 5B and 5D1 are not specific for CD44, TLR2 and TLR4 of living cells, respectively because corneum consists of dead cells (43).

HA4 suppressed hydrogen peroxide-induced damage and/or senescence but not in the presence of anti-TLR4 antibody (Fig. 5D2). Non-immun control IgG2b of the anti-TLR4 did not show change in the suppressive effect of HA4 (Fig. 5D2). HA4 (MW: 800) of HA4 + TLR4 (MW: 70,600) but not of HA4 + heat denatured TLR4 was not detected in the bottom solution under a MW filter (5,000) that TLR4 cannot go through, indicating that HA4 bound TLR4 (Fig. 5D3).

DNA microarray.

Proliferation inducer (Hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) and Fibroblast growth factor 1 (FGF1)), Differentiation inducer (HGF) and Differentiation marker (Keratin 1) were up-regulated by HA4 in human keratinocytes (Table 1), indicating that HA4 induced both proliferation and differentiation which coincide with the results of REKs and human neuro-spheres in Fig. 2. Cell death inducers (Daxx and Fas associated factor 1) was down-regulated and cell death suppressors (DnaJ homolog and HGF) were up-regulated by HA4 (Table 1),, indicating that HA4 suppresses cell death, which coincide with our previous study showing suppression of cell death by Hsp72 promotion and of ischemia-induced neural cell death (5-7).

Senescence inducers (growth hormone receptor and FGF23) were down-regulated and Senescence suppressors (FGF1 and HGF) were up-regulated by HA4 (Table 1), which coincide with the results of cellular senescence in Fig. 4.

Table 2 shows that HGF receptor (Met), FGF, and JNK (c-Jun kinases) phosphorylation and activation mediated by activated human TAK1 are significantly implicated in signaling pathway. The Met and FGF are coincide with up-regulation of HGF and FGF1 (Table 1). JNK (c-Jun kinases) phosphorylation and activation mediated by activated human TAK1, which is implicated in apoptosis or cell survival, or proliferation that is contained in HA4 functions present and previous our studies showed (Fig. 2A-2C) (5-7, 44).

Terms in up-regulation indicate differentiation and terms in down-regulation indicate suppression of proliferation (Table 3). The up-regulation of differentiation coincides with the results of filaggrin in REKs and human neuro-spheres (Fig. 2D and 2E). However, Table 3 does not coincide with Table 1 and 2, and the promotion of proliferation by HA4 (Fig. 2A, 2B and 2C).

DISCUSSION

HA4 induced partial Reprogramming, which is known to be followed by Tissue Regeneration, like newts though SIRT1 and SIRT1-Autophagy (Fig. 6A). The partial Reprogrammed cells have characteristics of stem and differentiated cells.

HA4 also generated HGF to induce both proliferation and differentiation, and HAS2 to produce HMWHA which promote proliferation via CD44 (Fig. 6A). Toole and Gross showed that HA that active synthesis of HA was demonstrated in de-differentiated blastema of the regenerating newt limb and that the proliferation followed the de-differentiation (45). M. Tammi

and R. Tammi indicated that HMWHA activated keratinocytes to facilitate epidermal tissue repair (19).

HMWHA is degraded into HA4 by hyaluronidases (PH20) (Fig. 6A). HGF activates SIRT1. Met: receptor of HGF (Fig. 6A). HA4-treated neural stem cells expressed β III Tubulin (β) while maintaining nestin (N), in other words HA4-treated neural stem cells have characteristics of stem and differentiated cells (Fig. 6A). The cells with characteristics of stem and differentiated cells have normal neural functions, because HA4 brought about recovery of walking ability and of neuronal ability indicated by histological and electro-physiological examinations in rat spinal cord injury (9-12).

HA4-induced stemness through SIRT1 and/or HGF (Fig. 6B). It was reported that proliferation differentiation are mutually exclusive (46). However, HA4 induced stemness, i.e., continuous coexistence of proliferation and differentiation which is shown in the newt Reprogramming (Fig. 6B). (35, 36). After injury, partial de-differentiation followed by proliferation is induced while maintaining differentiation characteristics, then re-differentiation is induced in epimorphosis of newt (35, 36).

Following 4 types of tissue regenerations were reported:

- 1) Stem cell mediated Regeneration: Unipotent stem cells differentiate into cells lost after injury.(47 Isabella Murray. Unipotent Stem Cells. EXPLORE stem cells. <https://www.explorestemcells.co.uk/unipotentstemcells.html>
- 2) Morphallaxis: the regeneration by transformation, renewal of existing body tissues which is found in hydra. The regenerated hydra forms smaller versions of the original hydra (48).
- 3) Compensatory regeneration: differentiated cells proliferate like hepatocytes (49).
- 4) Epimorphosis: regeneration of a specific part of an organism in a way that involves extensive cell proliferation of somatic stem cells, de-differentiation, and reformation, as well as formation of blastema, a mass of cells ca (35, 36).

The Stem cell mediated Regeneration, Morphallaxis and Compensatory regeneration are different from the HA4 regeneration.

Newt anterior gradient protein (nAG) is a growth factor for cultured newt blastemal cells and is sequentially expressed after amputation (50). HA4 induced SIRT1, HGF, FGF1 and HMWHA (Fig. 6C). Both HGF and FGF1 are demonstrated to stimulate SIRT1 expression (Fig. 6C). HGF induces HAS2 which is shown to produce HMWHA (Fig. 6C). Acidic environment brought by inflammation and ageing is reported to activate Hyal-1 to degrade HMWHA into HA4 (Fig. 6C). The inflammation, ageing and HAS2 expression are known to suppressed by SIRT1 (Fig. 6C). These things indicate that HA4 is endogenously produced by inflammation and ageing that is known to be weak and continuous inflammation (11, 12). SIRT1 suppresses production of HA4 as feedback regulation, indicating that HA4 constructs a self-tissue regeneration system with SIRT1 (Fig. 6C).

Surprisingly, HA4, the minimal HA in mammal and the maximal HA, 6,000 kDa HA of naked mole rats have many functions in common (Fig. 6D). The 6,000 kDa HA are linking to SIRT1, mediates the cancer resistance, contribute to their longevity in naked mole (51). HA with either 1.2 kDa or 6,000 kDa suppress tumor growth (52).

Conclusions

1. HA4 is endogenously produced in injuries or diseases with inflammation or in ageing, and constructs a self-tissue regeneration system through HGF, FGF1, HMWHA and SIRT1.
2. The HGF, FGF1, HMWHA and SIRT1 control HA4 production in the feedback regulation.

3. HA4 can induce tissue Regeneration through the newt type Reprogramming which contains de-differentiation, proliferation and re-differentiation, and characteristics of stem and differentiated cells.
4. The mammal minimal HA, 0.8 kDa HA, i.e., HA4 and the maximal HA, 6,000 kDa HA of the naked mole rats have many functions in common.

Figure 1

Fig. 1. Analyses of HA4. **A.** Anion exchange HPLC analyses (a-e) and FACE (f and g). **a.** standard HA4 (sHA4). 6: standard HA6, 8: standard HA8. **b.** standard HA6 (sHA6). 4: standard HA4. **c.** standard HA8 (sHA8), **d.** HA4 used in the present study. **e.** HA4 used in the present study that was treated with chondroitinase ABC to yield the HA disaccharides (HA2 & normal HA2, *). **f.** Line 1: standards (Std) Δ di-HA and Δ di-C0S, Line 2: HA4 used in the present study that was treated with chondroitinase ABC (Chase) to yield the HA disaccharides (HA2 & normal HA2; arrows). Line 3: HA4 used in the present study. Line 4: HA4 used in the present study that was treated with heat inactivated chondroitinase ABC (hChase). Line 5: standards (Std) HA4, HA6 and HA8. **g.** 2: standard HA2. **B.** Molecular structure of HA4 in the present study. GlcA: Glucuronic acid, GlcNAc: N-acetylglucosamine.

Figure 2

Fig. 2. HA4-induced proliferation (A-C), differentiation (D and E) and ectopic expressions

(F and G). A1. Murine growth rate of fertilized oocytes 48 hrs after fertilization = (No. of Morula cells 48 hrs / No. of 2 cells period cells 24 hrs) x100. **A2:** Mechanism of HA4 production immediately before fertilization which bind TLR4 just after fertilization. HAase in red: testicular hyaluronidase. M: cell membrane. **B-1.** Ki67, a marker of proliferation was detected even in the spinous-granular layers in HA4-treated REKs (arrowheads) not in the No-addition control (N). **B-2.** Number of Ki67⁺ cells per 200 x 200 μm^2 of the tissues. n=5, Mean \pm SD, **: p<0.01 versus the No-addition control (N), paired *t*-test. **C.** HA4-induced proliferation of NIH3T3 cells. MTS assay. **: P<0.01, vs N (No-addition control), paired *t*-test. **D.** Filaggrin immuno-staining. **E1.** human neuro-spheres treated with and without brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF, 25 ng/ml, **b**), HA4 (10 ng.ml. **c**) and BDNF (25 ng/ml) + HA4 (10 ng.ml) (**d**). **E2.** Immuno-staining of nestin (red) and b III Tubulun (Tubulin, green) in human neuro-spheres. **F1.** Immuno-staining of ΔNp63 (red). **F2.** ΔNp63^+ cells per 200 x 200 μm^2 of the tissues. n=5, Mean \pm SD, **: p<0.01 versus the No-addition control (N), paired *t*-test. H: HA4 10 ng/ml. **G.** K14 (a marker of basal layer keratinocytes. **H1 and H2.** Summarized illustrations of the changes by the HA4 in epidermal stem cells in REKs (**H1**) and neural stem cells (**H2**). N in black: No-addition control, Red letters: characterizations of stem cells, blue letters: characterizations of differentiated cells, size of letters: intensity of expression, Δ : ΔNp63 , K in red: K14, Ki: Ki67, f: Filaggrin, b : b III Tubulun.

Figure 3

Fig. 3. Induction of sirtuins by HA4. **A.** Immuno-staining of SIRT1 in REKs. **B.** Immuno-staining of SIRT1 in human keratinocytes monolayers. White arrows: telomere phase

keratinocytes, blue arrows: small round cells, i.e., stem cells. Concentration of HA4: 10 ng/ml. **C.** Immuno-staining of SIRT1 in human keratinocytes monolayers treated with HA4 (0.01-10 ng/ml). **D.** Immuno-staining of SIRT1 in human keratinocytes monolayers treated with several MW HA (10 ng/ml) and resveratrol (10 ng/ml). **E.** Western blotting of SIRT1 in REKs at Day 5. S/G: Ration of SIRT1 / GAPDH in intensity, N: No-addition control, Δ 2: unsaturated HA di-saccharides, Δ 4: unsaturated HA tetra-saccharides, C4: unsaturated chondroitin sulfate tetra-saccharides, concentration: 10 ng/ml. **F.** RT-qPCR of SIRT1 in human keratinocytes. 4: HA4, 6: HA6, 10: HA10, 35: 35 kDa HA, R: resveratrol, concentration: 10 ng/ml. **G.** SIRT1 deacetylase activity in human keratinocytes treated with HA4 (0.01-1.0 ng/ml). **H.** SIRT1 deacetylase activity in human keratinocytes. 2: unsaturated HA2, 3: HA3, 4: HA4, 6: HA6, 35: 35 kDa HA, 9: 900 kDa HA, C4: unsaturated chondroitin sulfate tetra-saccharides, R: resveratrol (3 μ M), concentration (except for resveratrol): 10 ng/ml, rSIRT1: recombinant human SIRT1, red bar: + NAD, blue bar: - NAD. **I.** SIRT6 deacetylase activity in human keratinocytes. 2: unsaturated HA2, 4: HA4, 6: HA6, 35: 35 kDa HA, 9: 900 kDa HA, R: resveratrol, concentration: 10 ng/ml. **J.** SIRT3 immuno-staining. **K.** SIRT6 immuno-staining.

Figure 4

Fig. 4. Effects of HA4 on senescence and inflammation. A. Senescence associated-b

Galactosidase staining of murine skin fibroblasts after 2 or 4 passages treated with or without 10 ng/ml of HA2, HA4, HA6, 900 kDa HA or resveratrol. **A1.** Light microscopical photographs of SA-beta Gal staining. **A2.** Number of SA-b Gal positive cells per 0.135 mm². N: no-addition control, 900: 900 kDa HA, Res: resveratrol. **: P<0.01 versus N (red bar), Dunnett multiple comparison test. **B.** Micrographs of human fibroblasts cultured until Hayflic limit. **a-d.** light microscopy. **e-i.** electron microscopy. **a.** No addition control at Day 20. **b.** No addition control at Day 40. **c.** No addition control at Day 50. Light blue indicates a cell shape. **d.** 10 ng/ml of HA4 at Day 50. **e.** No addition control at Day 50. **f.** Inset of **e.** **g and h.** No addition control at Day 40. **i.** 10 ng/ml of HA4 at Day 50. orange arrows: inclusion bodies (large phago-lysosome), red arrows: Autophagic vacuoles (small phago-lysosomes), blue arrows: mitochondria, bar in a: 10 µm, bars in e-h: 2 µm. **C1.** Mitochondrial membrane potential. **C2.** Immunostaining of. **a.** No-addition control at Day 40. **b.** No-addition control at Day 50. **c.** 10 ng/ml of HA4 at Day 50. **d.** HA4 (10 ng/ml) + EXT527 (20 nM), at Day 50. **e.** 900 kDa (1000 ng/ml) HA at Day 50. **f.** resveratrol (1000 ng/ml). **D. Effects of HA4 on cytokine productions in U937 cells treated with PMA and/or LPS.** N: No-addition, Dex: dexamethasone., * P<0.05, **: 0.01 versus No-addition (black bars), Dunnett multiple comparison test.

Figure 5

Fig. 5. Effects of HA4 on HA production, CD44 expression and rabbit corneal wound healing, and Binding assay of HA4 to toll like receptor 4 (TLR4). A1. HA production in

REKs. N: No-addition. **A2**. Inset of **A1**. Arrows: inter-cellular bridge, *: corneum. **A3**. Negative control by hyaluronidase from *Streptomyces hyalurolyticus* specific for HA. **A4**. HAS2 immunostaining in REKs. co: corneum. **B**. CD44 immunostaining in REKs. co: non-specific staining in corneum (co). **C1a**. Rabbit eyes of 24 hrs after injury. **C1b**. Wound area 24 hrs after injury. **C2a**. Rabbit eyes of 48 hrs after injury. **C2b**. Wound area 48 hrs after injury. **C3**. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Arrowheads: edges of migrating epithelial cells, arrows: epithelial cells. **D1**. Effects of HA4 on immuno-staining of TLR2 and TLR4. **D2**. Suppression of hydrogen peroxide -induced cellular senescence and damage by HA4. a-TLR4: anti-TLR4 antibody, IgG2a: non-immun control of the anti-TLR4. **D3**. Binding assay of HA4 to TLR4. Std: standard, T4: TLR4, hT4: heat denatured TLR4.

Figure 6

Fig. 6. Summarized illustration of effects of HA4 I. A1. Big phago-lysosomes and small

mitochondria were observed by electron-microscopy fibroblasts at Hayflick limit. The Big phago-lysosomes indicate indigestion of phagocytosed organelles. **A2.** Many Autophagic vacuoles and long mitochondria, which promote anti-senescence and Reprogramming, were detected in HA4-treated fibroblasts. **B1.** Organotypic 3D rat epidermal keratinocytes (REKs) consists of differentiated and basal layers which contain stem cells. **B2.** HA4 induced stem cell molecular markers in the differentiated layers, indicating that HA4-treated cells contain characteristics of stem and differentiated cells as shown in newt Reprogramming followed by tissue Regeneration. **C1.** Brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) differentiated human neural stem cells into neurons of which characteristic is in green and diminished stem cell characteristic (red). **C2.** HA4 induced differentiated the neural stem cells into neurons while maintaining the neural stem cell characteristic. HA4-treated cells contain characteristics of stem and differentiated cells. Yellow means green (differentiated cells) + red (stem cells) .

Figure 7

Fig. 7. Summarized illustration of effects of HA4 II. A. HA4-induced Tissue Regeneration. HA4 induced partial Reprogramming and Tissue Regeneration like newts though SIRT1 and SIRT1-Autophagy. The partial Reprogrammed cells have characteristics of stem and

differentiated cells. HA4 also generated HGF to induce both proliferation and differentiation, and HAS2 to produce high MW hyaluronan (HMWHA) which promote proliferation via CD44. HMWHA is degraded into HA4 by hyaluronidases (Hyal-1 and PH20). HGF activates SIRT1. Met: receptor of HGF. **B.** HA4-induced stemness through SIRT1 and/or HGF. Red arrows: differentiation, blue arrows: self-renewal. **C.** Production of HA4 through activated Hyal-1. FGF1: fibroblast growth factor 1. Both of HGF and FGF1 stimulate SIRT1 expression. HGF induces hyaluronan synthase 2 (HAS2) expression. SIRT1 suppresses HAS2 expression, and inflammation and ageing. **D.** Functions of HA depend on MW. The functions of HA4, almost minimal are shown in 6,000 kDa HA, which are linking to SIRT1 and contribute to their longevity and no tumor in naked mole rats.

Table 1. Gene expressions in DNA microarray

Table 2. Signaling pathways in DNA microarray

Table 3. Gene ontology of DNA microarray

Abbreviations

HA: hyaluronan, HMWHA: high molecular weight hyaluronan, GlcA: glucuronic acid, GlcNAc: Nacetyl glucosamine, HA4: hyaluronan tetra-saccharides, HA2: hyaluronan di-saccharides, HA3: hyaluronan tri-saccharides, HA5: hyaluronan penta-saccharides, HA6: hyaluronan hexa-saccharides, HA8: hyaluronan octa-saccharides, Δ HA2: unsaturated hyaluronan di-saccharides, Δ HA4: unsaturated hyaluronan tetra-saccharides, CS: chondroitin sulfate, Δ CS: unsaturated chondroitin sulfate, HPLC: High Performance Liquid Chromatography, FACE: Fluorophore-assisted carbohydrate electrophoresis, LPS: lipopolysaccharides (LPS) PMA: Phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate, TLR: toll like receptor, HAS: hyaluronan synthase, BDNF: brain neurotrophic growth factor, FGF: fibroblast growth factor, HGF: hepatocyte growth factor, REKs: organotypic 3D rat epidermal keratinocytes, sirt: sirtuin, K14: keratin 14, K10: keratin 10, Chase: chondroitinase, TAK1: TGF- β -activated kinase 1, JNK: c-jun kinase, Hsp72: heat shock protein 72, AMAC: 2-Aminoacridone, BSA: bovine serum albumin, H.E.: Hematoxylin-Eosin, HRP: horseradish peroxidase, DAB: 3,3'-diaminobenzidine, co: corneum, qRT-PCR: quantitative Reverse Transcription-Polymerase Chain Reaction, GAPDH: Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase

Ethics approval and consent to participate

We confirm that we have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

Consent for publication

We hereby provide consent for the publication of the manuscript detailed above, including any accompanying images or data contained within the manuscript that may directly or indirectly disclose our identities.

Availability of data and materials

Data, in anonymous format (according to data protection policy in the ethics agreement) is available on reasonable request.

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Author contributions

A.A. designed the experiments. A.A. and L. Z. performed and analyzed the experiments. A.A. wrote the manuscript. V. H. supervised the project.

Competing interests

All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data and Materials availability

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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